

Particle accumulation model in 3D reconstructed wall of a catalytic filter validated with time-resolved X-ray tomography

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Abstract

A transient pore-scale model of particle deposit formation in 3D microstructure of a catalytic filter wall is introduced. It predicts location of particle deposits, dynamics of their growth, transition from deep to cake filtration regime as well as the impact on flow field, pressure drop and filtration efficiency. The model is validated against time-resolved X-ray tomography (XRT) data acquired during a filtration experiment. The validated model is then used in transient simulations of the soot filtration process in several different microstructures using cordierite filter substrate with varied Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst distribution. The sample with the coating solely inside the wall pores provides the lowest initial pressure drop but suffers from low clean filtration efficiency and high pressure drop after the cake is formed. The sample with partial on-wall coating achieves not only a higher filtration efficiency but also a lower pressure drop in long-term operation.

Keywords: mathematical modeling, CFD, DPF, GPF, automotive exhaust

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1. Introduction

One of the main pollutants present in exhaust gas from combustion engines burning carbonaceous fuels is the particulate matter (PM). Especially the fine particulate matter, comprising particles of diameter under $2.5 \mu\text{m}$, has a widely reported negative influence on human health [1]. All over the world, the PM pollution is controlled via various emission limits. In Europe, the particulate matter has been restricted not only by its mass but also a number of particles since the norm Euro 6c (2017) for both diesel and gasoline engines. The latest legislation, Euro 6d (2020), requires the particle number emissions under $9 \times 10^{11} \#/\text{km}$ with the conformity factor of 1.5 during the real drive emissions (RDE) test, including the cold start phase [2]. For Euro 7, it is expected that the range of counted particles will be extended down to 10 nm (the current size limit is 23 nm and the smaller particles are excluded from the emission tests).

In order to meet the legal requirements on PM emissions, automotive exhaust gas aftertreatment systems are commonly equipped with particulate filters (PF), referred also as diesel particulate filters (DPF) and gasoline particulate filters (GPF) according to their application [2, 3, 4, 5]. Furthermore, PF can be combined with catalysts for conversion of gaseous pollutants to create a catalytic filter. The catalytic filter is a monolithic reactor comprising parallel channels that are alternately plugged at one end. Such a design forces the exhaust gas to flow through the channels walls that are porous and provide (i) filtration of particles (soot and ash), and (ii) conversion of gaseous pollutants in contact with the catalytic material.

A filter coated with three-way catalyst is beneficial in the exhaust gas aftertreatment systems for gasoline engines [6, 7, 8]. The filters in diesel engine vehicles is often combined with diesel oxidation catalyst [9, 10] or with a catalyst for selective catalytic reduction of nitrogen oxides [11, 12]. All these devices need to meet requirements that are typically anti-correlated: low pressure drop ver-

29 sus high catalytic conversion and filtration efficiency. These key performance
30 parameters are strongly influenced by the device geometry, micro-structural
31 morphology and PM loading [13].

32 The device geometry and micro-structural morphology is controlled during
33 the filter production in order to optimize its performance. It was demonstrated
34 that the filter substrates with non-uniform distribution of porosity, in particu-
35 lar those with a thin layer of reduced pore size on top of the wall, may achieve
36 improved filtration performance [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. Previous studies
37 of filters coated with a catalytic layer included experimental work [22, 23, 24]
38 and numerical models based on computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to identify
39 suitable coating structure and location inside or on the filter walls and its impact
40 on transport-limited conversion of gaseous pollutants [25, 26, 27], clean filtra-
41 tion efficiency [28] and pressure drop [29]. In parallel, models based on lattice
42 Boltzmann method (LBM) were developed for the computation of clean filtra-
43 tion efficiency and catalytic conversion [30, 31]. The mentioned studies worked
44 with 3D reconstructed section of porous wall with realistic catalyst distribution
45 obtained from X-ray tomography (XRT) scans, however, they considered just a
46 clean particulate filter.

47 Such a state corresponds only to a fraction of the filter life span due to the
48 strong influence of soot accumulation on its performance. The soot/ash cake
49 buildup improves the filtration performance, but it also increases its pressure
50 drop and, consequently, the engine fuel consumption [32]. To identify the most
51 suitable life-span morphology of a catalytic filter wall, a micro-structural model
52 taking into account the growth of particle deposits inside the filter is required.
53 The first models of particle accumulation in 3D digital prototypes of porous
54 DPF wall were presented by Konstandopoulos, A.G. and Kostoglou, M. and
55 Lorentzou, S. and Vlachos, N. [16]. Though the models using a layer of packed
56 particles as an approximation of the real wall structure are still being used
57 [21], the development of X-ray tomography enabled reliable 3D reconstructions
58 of real filter structures [22], which drawn modelling efforts in that direction
59 [25, 26, 28, 30, 31]. Li et al. [33] introduced an LBM model incorporating the soot

60 accumulation. However, their model treats the soot deposits as an impermeable
61 wall, similar to filter wall, which results in a nonphysically high pressure drop
62 and limited percolation. Recently, more realistic LBM model including the
63 soot cake permeability was developed Yamamoto and Yagasaki [34], enabling a
64 parametric study of particle size influence on the filtration process. However,
65 that model was limited to a bare filter without any catalytic coating. A detailed
66 review of various filtration models working at 3D pore-scale level as well as using
67 a simplified 1D collector approach is provided by [35].

68 In this paper, we present a transient model of particle deposit formation in
69 3D microstructure of a catalytic filter wall, including the impact of coated cat-
70 alytic material. In contrast to the LBM-based models [30, 33, 34], the presented
71 filtration model is built on a weak coupling between an Eulerian CFD solver
72 used to compute the flow field inside the filter wall and a Lagrangian tracking
73 of soot particles. The soot deposits are transformed into porous zones in the
74 CFD model and their volume is periodically updated on the basis of Lagrangian
75 solver results. In turn, the deposited soot affects gas velocity and pressure field
76 in the filter wall.

77 The newly proposed model is first validated against the data obtained by
78 time-resolved, in-situ XRT of aerosol filtration [36] and then used for transient
79 simulations of the soot filtration process in several different microstructures us-
80 ing cordierite filter substrate with various Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst distributions.
81 Attention is paid to the prediction of particle deposits location, dynamics of
82 their growth, transition from deep to cake filtration regime as well as the im-
83 pact on flow field, pressure drop and filtration efficiency, all depending on the
84 distribution of catalyst in the filter microstructure. The ultimate goal is to iden-
85 tify suitable coating locations with respect to long-term operation including the
86 impact of accumulated particles.

Figure 1: Simplified scheme of the experimental set-up.

87 2. Experimental

88 The 3D microstructures used as simulation domains were obtained from
 89 the processed XRT images. First, a bare cordierite filter marked as BF0 was
 90 examined by time-resolved in-situ XRT during a filtration experiment at the
 91 I13-2 Diamond Manchester Imaging branchline at Diamond Light Source. The
 92 experimental setup is depicted in Figure 1. The cordierite filter had 300 cpsi,
 93 total length 29 mm, channel plug length 1 mm, wall thickness $216 \mu\text{m}$, and wall
 94 porosity 63%. During the filtration experiment, the gas inlet was allowed just to
 95 a single central channel. Using the volumetric flow rate of 21 ml/min, the mean
 96 superficial gas velocity through the wall was 0.0026 m s^{-1} . The inlet gas velocity
 97 in the open channel was 0.23 m s^{-1} ; note that just one from nine channels was
 98 open during the experiment. When recalculated to a standard filter set-up with
 99 the 1:1 arrangement of open and closed channels, the flow rate corresponds
 100 to gas hourly space velocity of approximately $10\,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The uniformity of
 101 wall flow along the channel was checked by a channel-scale CFD simulation,
 102 see Figure A.1 in AppendixA. The temperature during the experiment was
 103 $T=298 \text{ K}$.

Figure 2: Particle size distribution of aerosolized ZnO powder measured in the experiment and used in the model validation simulations. Total steady concentration of particles was $N_p = 1.9 \times 10^9 \# \text{ cm}^{-3}$, increased five times during the start-up.

104 A direct experimental imaging of soot deposition in-situ is unfeasible due to
 105 its low density. Therefore, TiO_2 or ZnO nanoparticles have been proposed as
 106 suitable alternatives that provide sufficient contrast and allow reliable segmenta-
 107 tion of the particle deposits inside the porous filter wall [36]. In this experiment,
 108 ZnO powder was used as particulate matter and the results were then utilized
 109 for validation of the newly developed transient filtration model. Figure 2 shows
 110 the measured particle size distribution in the ZnO aerosol. At the start-up, the
 111 inlet concentration of particles temporarily increased and only then reached a
 112 stable level. This might be due to dust generator start-up or re-entrainment
 113 of previously deposited particles in the lines. The temporary higher inlet con-
 114 centration at the start-up was accounted for in the simulation, similarly as the
 115 actual density of ZnO particles that differs from soot, Sections 3.2–3.3.

116 The time-resolved XRT consisted of acquiring tomograms of the region of
 117 interest within the filter sample, then flowing aerosolized ZnO powder through
 118 the sample, redirecting the aerosol flow to bypass, and then re-imaging the
 119 region of interest. This was repeated to create a time series data set with images
 120 acquired after 0 s, 10 s, 30 s, 50 s and 110 s of cumulative aerosol loading.

121 For these tomograms a radiographic projection was acquired every 0.1 in an

122 180 fly scan (1800 projections) with exposure times of 0.03 s. Flat and dark
123 field images were obtained at each time step in the experiment. The pink beam
124 configuration at I13-2 with several harmonic peaks was used. The ID gap was set
125 at 5 mm, and the Pt mirror was used; this already filtered the beam sufficiently
126 so no extra filter was installed. Thus, the spectrum reaching the sample ranged
127 from 6 to 29 keV, the peak flux was at 17 keV. The $2\times$ objective was used for
128 this workflow coupled to a LuAg scintillator. This $2\times$ lens resulted in a total
129 $4\times$ magnification with pixel size of $1.625\ \mu\text{m}$. At the start of the beamtime the
130 spectrum was optimised such that sufficient brightness and contrast between
131 the deposit phase and background was observed in the radiographs.

132 Image processing and segmentation steps allowed the dataset to be seg-
133 mented into pore/background, cordierite filter, and ZnO deposit phases for later
134 quantification. Projections were reconstructed using the Filtered Back Projec-
135 tion algorithm from Astra in Savu [37] with ring removal, distortion correction,
136 and dark-flat field correction [38, 39]. Each 3D image in the time series was then
137 rotated, translated and cropped to the region of interest, a $553\times 1380\times 2440\ \mu\text{m}^3$
138 section. A histogram matching algorithm was then applied across the whole time
139 series dataset.

140 Each of these 3D images in the time series was then registered onto the
141 zeroth image so that features were aligned across the times series. The zeroth
142 image is that which has no ZnO loading within it. The registration used meth-
143 ods from the Python distribution of SimpleITK. At this point the dataset was
144 ready for segmentation. First a mask of the cordierite filter in the zeroth image
145 was obtained using a simple intensity threshold. This was then applied to the
146 ZnO loaded images to mask out the cordierite phase such that the remaining
147 high intensity pixels in the image belonged to the ZnO deposit, allowing for
148 segmentation of the ZnO phase. By then combining the cordierite mask and
149 ZnO mask from each time step we achieved full segmentation of the dataset.

150 In addition to the time-resolved XRT, a series of bare and coated catalytic
151 filters was scanned by standard XRT at New Technologies Research Centre in
152 Pilsen to obtain the information about the wall microstructure and coating lo-

Table 1: Sample description: cell density N , thickness of the filter wall δ , volume fraction of free pores in the filter wall ε_f , volume fraction of catalytic material in the filter wall $\varphi_{c,\text{wall}}$, volume fraction of catalytic material total φ_c .

Sample	N [cpsi]	δ [μm]	ε_f [1]	$\varphi_{c,\text{wall}}$ [1]	φ_c [1]
BF0	300	216	0.63	0	0
BF1	300	216	0.66	0	0
CF1	300	216 + 0 ^a	0.36 ^b	0.28	0.28
CF2	300	216 + 21 ^a	0.43 ^b	0.20	0.29
CF3	300	216 + 34 ^a	0.48 ^b	0.14	0.30

^a Including the coated catalyst layer on the wall.

^b Pores in the substrate wall remaining unoccupied after the coating process, excluding smaller internal pores in the coating.

153 cation. These samples were prepared by vacuum washcoating of Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃
154 catalyst suspensions [23] on a cordierite filter substrate with 300 cpsi, wall thick-
155 ness 216 μm and porosity of 66 %. The bare substrate sample from this series
156 is denoted as BF1, and the related coated catalytic filters are denoted as CF1,
157 CF2, and CF3. These catalytic filter samples use the same catalyst loading and
158 differ only by the coating location: in-wall, combined on-wall and in-wall, and
159 prevailing on-wall for CF1, CF2 and CF3, respectively.

160 The samples were scanned by X-ray tomograph Xradia MicroXCT 400 with
161 source voltage 60 kV and power 6 W. The medium-size detector and 10 \times optical
162 magnification results in resolution 2016 \times 2016 pixels and voxel size 1.113 μm .
163 These XRT scans were segmented by brightness thresholds using the software
164 package Fiji/ImageJ [40, 41] to identify substrate, coating and pore morphology
165 [22, 25]. The structures BF1, CF1, CF2 and CF3 were then utilized in a simu-
166 lation parametric study revealing the coating location influence on the transient
167 soot filtration process.

168 Based on the processed and segmented XRT images, computational mesh
169 for simulations was generated in OpenFOAM [42]. An illustrative reconstruc-
170 tion procedure of coated filter sample CF2 can be seen in Figure 3. A cut out

Figure 3: A reconstruction procedure of coated filter sample CF2 demonstrated on a small section of the wall ($111 \times 187 \times 111 \mu\text{m}^3$) a) one slice from 3D scan of the filter channel with the segmented substrate (white), catalytic coating (red), and free pores (black); b) surface representation of the wall subsection with substrate in grey and coating in yellow; c) computational mesh refined near coating and substrate interfaces. Flow direction y goes from top to bottom.

171 of the XRT data (Figure 3a) was transformed into a surface representation of
 172 present solid faces as depicted in Figure 3b. These were used for mesh genera-
 173 tion by snappyHexMesh tool distributed with OpenFOAM, Figure 3c. In case
 174 of catalytic filters, the mesh includes also the coated catalyst zones so that gas
 175 transport through the coating is enabled in general. The meshes are unstruc-
 176 tured with local refinement in the vicinity of the solid walls and at the coating
 177 boundary. The used computational domains ideally cover complete thickness
 178 of the filter wall and approximately one half of the channel width with final
 179 dimensions around $630 \times 320 \times 223 \mu\text{m}^3$. Each mesh consists of approximately
 180 60 million cells.

Figure 4: Block scheme of the proposed computational framework.

181 **3. Mathematical model**

182 The reconstructed filter structures were employed in a computational frame-
 183 work represented by Figure 4. The proposed framework includes several inter-
 184 connected solvers: flow, diffusion and reaction [25], solid particle movement [28],
 185 and the newly developed model for particles accumulation, growth of the filtra-
 186 tion deposits and cake formation. In this paper we focus solely on the particles
 187 movement and accumulation in the wall microstructure during the filtration
 188 process.

189 Based on the results from [43], similarities between gasoline and diesel en-
 190 gines, and classification of coupling schemes and interactions between parti-
 191 cles and flow introduced in [44], only one way coupling between the particles
 192 and the flow is assumed. Similarly, because the soot is diluted in the system
 193 with volumetric fraction below 0.1 ppm [43] and comprises small particles of
 194 $d_p \lesssim 160$ nm [28], instantaneous effects of the deposition on the flow are ne-

195 glected and the system is simulated as decoupled, i.e., the flow is assumed at
 196 steady state during the simulation of solid particles movement and recalculated
 197 only after a deposition of significant volume as will be discussed in more detail
 198 in Section 3.3.

199 3.1. Model of gas flow

200 The fluid flow is assumed laminar and simulated in the whole domain si-
 201 multaneously, including free pores, catalytic coating, and already accumulated
 202 particle deposits. For this purpose, the following variant of the Navier-Stokes
 203 equations for isothermal incompressible flow is considered,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) - \nabla \cdot (\nu \nabla \mathbf{u}) &= -\nabla p + \mathbf{s} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

204 where \mathbf{u} corresponds to the fluid velocity, p to the kinematic pressure, and the
 205 coefficient ν denotes the fluid kinematic viscosity. Kinematic viscosity ν of the
 206 gas flowing through the filter wall is calculated from:

$$\nu = \frac{\mu}{\rho}, \quad \mu = \frac{bT^{3/2}}{T + S}, \quad (2)$$

207 where ρ is the fluid density computed from the ideal gas equation and μ stands
 208 for the dynamic viscosity given by the Sutherland equation (2), with the pa-
 209 rameters $b = 1.458 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1/2}$ and $S = 110.4 \text{ K}$ [45].

210 The additional source term \mathbf{s} in equation (1) reflects the additional resistance
 211 to the flow present in the catalytic coating as well as in the formed particle
 212 deposits, which both possess internal porosity. This source term is based on the
 213 Darcy permeability model [46] and it is defined as

$$\mathbf{s} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{0} & \text{in free pores} \\ -\varphi_s \frac{\nu}{\kappa_s} \mathbf{u} & \text{in soot deposits} \\ -\frac{\nu}{\kappa_c} \mathbf{u} & \text{in coated zones,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

214 where κ_s and κ_c are the local Darcy permeabilities of the corresponding porous
 215 zones. The value of κ_c for the catalytic coating is estimated from the Carman-

Table 2: Structural parameters of the deposited soot and surrogate ZnO particles.

Parameter	Symbol	ZnO deposits	soot deposits
Particle size distribution	d_p	10–1000 nm, Figure 2	15–150 nm, Figure 5 [49]
Particle density	ρ_p	5600 kg m ⁻³	1000 kg m ⁻³ [50]
Deposit density	ρ_s	2800 kg m ⁻³	90 kg m ⁻³ [48]
Deposit porosity	ε_s	0.5	0.91
Deposit permeability	κ	7.69×10^{-14} m ²	7.69×10^{-14} m ² [48]

216 Kozeny equation [47] based on the porosity and characteristic diameter of par-
 217 ticles forming the zone presented in [25] and the $\kappa_c = 2.76 \times 10^{-15}$ m². The
 218 structural parameters of deposited soot and surrogate ZnO particles are pro-
 219 vided in Table 2. In the first approximation, ZnO deposit permeability was set
 220 to the same value as reported for the soot cake [48]. In order to account for a
 221 smooth and continuous growth of particle deposits, φ_s marks the actual local
 222 volume fraction of particle deposit in each finite volume cell, $\varphi_s = V_s/V_{\text{cell}}$.

223 The boundary of the solution domain was divided in three sections (inlet,
 224 outlet and walls). At the inlet, we apply a uniform inlet velocity in the direc-
 225 tion orthogonal to the wall (y axis) and a zero-gradient boundary condition for
 226 the pressure. At the outlet, constant pressure and so-called inlet-outlet bound-
 227 ary condition for \mathbf{u} is used, which stabilises the calculation. No-slip boundary
 228 condition was specified at the walls and the remaining domain boundaries.

229 Such defined mathematical model of flow was solved by the OpenFOAM
 230 toolbox [42], employing the porousSimpleFoam steady state solver that uses the
 231 consistent SIMPLE algorithm [51, 52] to compute the pressure-velocity coupling.

232 3.2. Model of particle movement

233 The particle movement model is based on Lagrangian tracking of individual
 234 spherical particles moving through the actual reconstructed 3D media [28]. Be-
 235 cause the soot particles in the studied system are small and sparsely distributed,
 236 particle-particle interactions are neglected. The initial velocity of each particle
 237 entering the system is equal to gas velocity $u_{y,\text{in}}$. The particle motion inside

238 the system is governed by the Newton's second law,

$$\rho_p V_p \frac{d\mathbf{u}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_D + \mathbf{F}_B, \quad (4)$$

239 where ρ_p is particle density, V_p is volume of the particle and \mathbf{u}_p is its velocity.
 240 On the right hand side, \mathbf{F}_D and \mathbf{F}_B stand for the drag and the Brownian force,
 241 respectively, acting on the microscopic solid particle at the time t [28]. The
 242 laminar drag force \mathbf{F}_D is represented by the Stokes law taking into account the
 243 pre-calculated gas flow field \mathbf{u} ,

$$\mathbf{F}_D = \frac{3\pi\mu d_p}{C_C} (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_p), \quad (5)$$

244 where d_p is the particle diameter and C_C is the Cunningham slip factor [53]

$$C_C = 1 + \frac{2\lambda}{d_p} \left[1.257 + 0.4 \exp\left(-1.1 \frac{d_p}{2\lambda}\right) \right]. \quad (6)$$

245 λ stands for the molecular mean free path. The calculation of Brownian force
 246 utilizes the vector of zero-mean independent Gaussian random numbers of unit
 247 variance \mathbf{G} [28],

$$\mathbf{F}_B = \rho_p V_p \mathbf{G} \sqrt{\frac{\pi S_0}{\Delta t_p}}, \quad \mathbf{G}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (7)$$

248 The variable S_0 is linked to the spectral intensity of the Gaussian white noise
 249 and provides the Brownian force amplitude [54],

$$S_0 = \frac{216\nu k_B T}{\pi^2 \rho d_p^5 \left(\frac{\rho_p}{\rho}\right)^2 C_C}, \quad (8)$$

250 where ρ is density of the gas. The integration step for particle movement Δt_p
 251 solution according to equation (4) was 1×10^{-6} s, which was necessary for
 252 capturing the particle trajectory through the system including Brownian motion
 253 effects [28].

254 3.3. Particle deposition model

255 *Particle trapping.* In line with the clean filtration study [28], the probability
 256 of particle trapping is assumed $\mathcal{P} = 1$ upon particle-wall and particle-coating
 257 contact. To deal with the growing particle deposits, we must define also the

Figure 5: Gasoline soot particle size distribution used in the parametric simulation study of soot accumulation. Total concentration of particles was $N_p = 1 \times 10^6 \# \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Based on the data reported in [49].

258 probability of trapping in a cell that is partly occupied by the already accumu-
 259 lated particles. In the first approximation, this trapping probability corresponds
 260 to the volume fraction of deposits in the particular cell, $\mathcal{P} = \varphi_s$. The test is
 261 implemented as a comparison of \mathcal{P} with a randomly generated, uniformly dis-
 262 tributed number. This test is performed for each particle just once in each cell
 263 on its trajectory. Once the particle is trapped, the corresponding increase in
 264 the local deposit volume is

$$\Delta V_s = \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_s} V_p = \frac{1}{1 - \varepsilon_s} V_p, \quad (9)$$

265 where ρ_p and ρ_s are densities of a single particle and porous solid deposit,
 266 respectively, and ε_s is porosity of the deposit. The parameters of ZnO and
 267 soot particle deposits are summarized in Table 2. The considered particle size
 268 distributions of ZnO and soot are provided in Figure 2 and Figure 5, respectively.

269 The growth of particle deposits inevitably includes situations when the par-
 270 ticles are trapped in almost fully occupied cell with $\varphi_s \lesssim 1$ and adding the
 271 corresponding deposit volume would lead to $V_s > V_{\text{cell}}$, i.e., $\varphi_s > 1$, which is
 272 physically unfeasible. To deal with this issue while keeping the particle mass
 273 and volume balance, a localised redistribution of trapped particles from the

Figure 6: Expected behaviour of the particle deposit redistribution algorithm on walls. The fully occupied cells are magenta, the source cell is bright. The excess particle volume is redistributed in the direction of white arrows first and later in the direction of yellow arrows. The target cells are in blue-green color shades indicating lower volume fractions of particle deposits φ_s .

274 overloaded cells was developed.

275 *Particle deposit redistribution.* The demands on particle redistribution model
 276 are as follows. First, the soot should be redistributed in a physically meaningful
 277 manner. Second, the algorithm needs to be computationally efficient, robust,
 278 and easily parallelized. Unfortunately, the aforementioned tasks seem to be
 279 anti-correlated.

280 The expected algorithm behaviour is demonstrated in Figure 6. The code
 281 needs to take into account a possibility of $\varphi_s > 1$ in a cell surrounded by cells
 282 in which $\varphi_s \geq 1$ already. Furthermore, the source cell Ω_P with $\varphi_s > 1$ can be
 283 placed either on an impermeable wall or on a pre-existing continuous layer of
 284 cells with $\varphi_s = 1$. The problem is mitigated by (i) redistributing the trapped
 285 particles between the cells via artificially-defined face fluxes, combined with
 286 (ii) a *tick-tock* approach to construction of these face fluxes for φ_s modification.
 287 Concentrating on the source cell Ω_P with $\varphi_{s,P} > 1$, in each odd step of the
 288 algorithm, only the faces shared with the neighbouring cells $\Omega_N \in \{\Omega_N\}_P$ with
 289 $\varphi_{s,N} < 1$ are considered for particle deposit redistribution in such a manner
 290 that $\varphi_{s,P} = 1$ after the algorithm step. In each even algorithm step, the already
 291 exploited faces of the cell Ω_P are not re-used. But, if required, the previously

292 unused faces shared with the neighbouring cells $\Omega_N \in \{\Omega_N\}_P$ having $\varphi_{s,N} \geq 1$
 293 are utilised. This approach allows to increase the stencil available for the soot re-
 294 distribution by one layer of cells each two algorithm iterations, while preserving
 295 the required algorithm behaviour. The developed algorithm for redistribution
 296 of the deposited particles was implemented in the OpenFOAM library and is
 297 available in a repository [55, 56].

298 Finally, after the simulated particle deposition period Δt_{sim} , the gas flow
 299 field is updated, reflecting the changed morphology of the porous structure,
 300 and the simulation continues in the loop as described in Figure 4. One pos-
 301 sible strategy could be to adapt the value of Δt_{sim} for flow field recalculation
 302 according to the deposit growth rate, i.e., to trigger the flow field recalcula-
 303 tion only after a significant increase in the deposit volume. However, for the
 304 case of low filtration efficiency and/or low inlet concentration of particles, this
 305 would result in an extremely long Δt_{sim} . In combination with the fixed internal
 306 time-step of 1×10^{-6} s in the particle movement simulation, this would lead to
 307 computationally expensive simulations.

308 To make the computation faster, we propose an alternative approach. The
 309 growth of particle deposits is simulated at a virtually increased particle concen-
 310 tration $N_{\text{p,sim}}$ in the inlet gas, leading to an accelerated soot loading compared
 311 to the real particle concentration $N_{\text{p,real}}$, Table 3. The acceleration factor is

$$\frac{\Delta t_{\text{real}}}{\Delta t_{\text{sim}}} = \frac{N_{\text{p,sim}}}{N_{\text{p,real}}} . \quad (10)$$

312 For example, when using ten times higher inlet concentration of particles, the
 313 simulated particle deposition process is ten times faster than in reality. The fil-
 314 tration efficiency increases from bare filter samples to the filters with catalytic
 315 coating, with the on-wall coated samples typically exhibiting the highest filtra-
 316 tion efficiency [28]. The values of $N_{\text{p,sim}}$ in Table 3 reflect this trend. The initial
 317 estimates of $N_{\text{p,sim}}$ were set according to the expected deposit formation rate
 318 in each sample based on the initially simulated clean filtration efficiency and,
 319 if necessary, revised after few time steps of transient accumulation simulation.
 320 The final $N_{\text{p,sim}}$ values used in the simulations are provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Simulation parameters for transient particle deposition.

Sample	$N_{p,\text{real}}$ ($\# \text{ cm}^{-3}$)	$N_{p,\text{sim}}$ ($\# \text{ cm}^{-3}$)	Δt_{sim} (s)	Δt_{real} (s)
BF0 – ZnO	1.9×10^9 *	1.90×10^{10} *	0.5	5
BF1 – soot	1×10^6	2.74×10^{10}	0.5	13700
CF1 – soot	1×10^6	3.42×10^9	0.5	1710
CF2 – soot	1×10^6	1.71×10^9	0.5	856
CF3 – soot	1×10^6	8.55×10^8	0.5	428

* The number concentrations of ZnO particles $N_{p,\text{real}}$ increased five times during the initial 10 s of the experiment; $N_{p,\text{sim}}$ was adjusted accordingly.

321 With this strategy, it was possible to keep a constant flow recalculation time-
 322 step $\Delta t_{\text{sim}} = 0.5$ s in all simulations. Note that this time step is still an order
 323 of magnitude longer than the mean residence time of gas in the wall (ca. 0.02 s
 324 at $u_{y,\text{in}} = 0.01 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), thus providing a sufficient period for transient particle
 325 trapping simulation. The time evolution of particle deposits obtained from the
 326 accelerated simulation was then scaled back to the real particle concentration
 327 using equation (10). The real concentration of surrogate ZnO particles in the
 328 validation experiment, $N_{p,\text{real}}$ in Table 3, was obtained by integrating the mea-
 329 sured particle size distribution, Figure 2. The soot particle concentration $N_{p,\text{real}}$
 330 for the subsequent parametric simulation study was set to $10^6 \# \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which
 331 is within the reported span for gasoline engines [57, 13].

332 4. Results

333 4.1. Model validation

334 A time-resolved XRT experiment during the filtration process, described in
 335 Section 2, was used for the model validation, considering ZnO particle size dis-
 336 tribution presented in Figure 2. The ZnO particle density is higher than that of
 337 soot particle, Table 2. This is accounted for in the model as the particle density
 338 is one of the input parameters used for the calculation of particle momentum
 339 and related forces during the filtration simulation, see equations (4), (7) and
 340 (8).

Figure 7: Evolution of particle deposits in a 3D reconstructed section of the BF0 filter wall as observed by time-resolved XRT during the experiment (a-d), and predicted by the simulation (e-h). Substrate = grey, particles = red, snapshot times $t = 10$ s (a,e), $t = 30$ s (b,f), $t = 50$ s (c,g), and $t = 110$ s (d,h). Flow direction y goes from top to bottom.

Figure 8: Averaged 1D profiles of the deposited particles over the filter wall during the filtration process. Comparison of model predictions and time-resolved XRT during the experiment.

341 The predicted evolution of particle deposits is visualised in Figure 7, where
 342 the model predictions are compared to the experimental observation from XRT
 343 scans. For the visualisation of particle deposits in the simulations, the cells
 344 occupied by more than 10% (i.e., with local volume fraction $\varphi_{s,P} > 0.1$) are
 345 displayed in red colour. Note that the smallest deposits are not detected by the
 346 XRT due to de-noising and threshold algorithms that must be applied to avoid
 347 artefacts. Thus, the experimental data show only larger domains of aggregated
 348 particles. Nevertheless, it can be seen that the location and dynamics of the
 349 deposits formation in the simulation and experiment correspond reasonably well.
 350 Most of the particles are captured in the top part of the wall, but some of them
 351 penetrate deep into the wall.

352 This is further quantified by the averaged 1D profiles of the deposited par-
 353 ticles through the the filter wall in Figure 8. The coordinate y corresponds to
 354 the top-down direction in Figure 7, and at each y location the averaging was
 355 performed over the entire xz plane (represented by a slice of the computational

356 mesh cells). The external surface of wall is located near $y = 50 \mu\text{m}$. The peak
357 of captured particles exhibits its maximum ca 5-10 microns below the external
358 surface, i.e., around $y = 55\text{--}60 \mu\text{m}$. A considerable amount of particles still
359 penetrate up to $30 \mu\text{m}$ deep inside the wall. Then there is a tail of deposits at
360 much lower but still detectable amount up to $y = 145 \mu\text{m}$, i.e., 95 microns deep
361 into the wall. The relatively fast decrease of the particle volume fraction at
362 that location suggests that there may be some pore neck or other morphological
363 feature that prevents further penetration of particles. The deposits deeper in
364 the wall ($y > 150 \mu\text{m}$) are only minor.

365 Figure 8 confirms good overall agreement of the model predictions and XRT
366 scan both in terms of spatial and temporal evolution. A minor difference (few
367 microns) can be seen in the location of the peak near the wall entrance. The
368 model predicts slightly deeper penetration while the deposits by XRT are lo-
369 cated more towards the external surface. The enhanced particle deposition on
370 the external surface might be influenced by electrostatic forces that were not
371 considered in the simulation. The biggest difference is in the peak value at
372 $t = 110\text{ s}$, where the model predicts much sharper peak compared to the XRT
373 scan. This could be caused by the re-entrainment and secondary movement of
374 particle agglomerates, which is not included in the model yet.

375 The reason for sudden decrease in the amount of deposited particles in the
376 middle of the wall around $y = 145 \mu\text{m}$ is further explored in Figures 9–11. The
377 xz slice through the wall at $y = 127 \mu\text{m}$ (i.e., $77 \mu\text{m}$ deep) shows a significant
378 accumulation of particles in a pore located in the upper right quadrant, and
379 another one in the lower right quadrant, with only minor contributions of other
380 locations, Figure 9. The particle deposition regions predicted by the model agree
381 reasonably well with the XRT observations during the filtration experiment.
382 Deeper in the wall, Figure 10, the deposits are observed in the same xz locations,
383 however, the corresponding pores get narrower, which is particularly visible for
384 the pores in the upper right quadrant. Finally, Figure 11 shows the situation
385 at $y = 174 \mu\text{m}$, which is ca. $124 \mu\text{m}$ deep inside the wall. Here the region in
386 upper right quadrant shows only minimum deposited particles. This indicates

387 that most of the particles were trapped in a narrower and more tortuous part
388 of the pores located above, cf. Figure 10. There are just two minor deposits
389 in the lower right quadrant, the locations of which agree in the simulation and
390 experiment. Considering the simplifying assumptions of the model as well as
391 detection limits of the XRT, one cannot expect perfect voxel-to-voxel agreement
392 between the simulation and experiment, nevertheless, Figures 8–11 demonstrate
393 that the model is able to predict correctly the locations of increased particle
394 accumulation in 3D structure of the filter wall.

395 *4.2. Coating location parametric study*

396 The validated model was subsequently used in a simulation study of the
397 catalytic coating location influencing the filtration process. The samples CF1,
398 CF2 and CF3 have similar amount of coating but different location, while the
399 sample BF1 is a bare substrate structure obtained by virtually removing the
400 catalytic coating from the sample CF1. Soot particle size distribution used
401 in this study is described in Figure 5 with the related parameters provided
402 in Tables 2 and 3. The soot accumulation simulations are computed at the
403 superficial gas velocity through wall $u_{y,\text{in}} = 0.01 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at temperature 453 K.
404 Note that the considered temperature is higher than room temperature, which
405 affects gas viscosity and needs to be taken into account when interpreting the
406 resulting values of pressure drop.

407 Figure 12 compares the samples BF1, CF1, CF2, CF3 in terms of their wall
408 microstructure (a-d) as well as the distribution of soot deposits formed before
409 reaching the filtration efficiency 99.9% (e-h). The clean filtration efficiency of all
410 samples is lower than that, which means that open pathways through the wall
411 pores must have been closed (at least locally) by the deposited soot in order
412 to reach the nearly complete filtration efficiency. This process took a different
413 amount of time for each sample as will be discussed in more detail later.

414 The bare substrate BF1 had to accumulate the highest amount of soot and
415 the soot particles penetrated the whole wall, Figure 12e. In contrast, the in-wall
416 coated sample CF1 with the identical substrate structure needs a significantly

Figure 9: Comparison of the predicted and scanned particle deposits for time 50 s at $y = 127 \mu\text{m}$, which is ca. $77 \mu\text{m}$ deep inside the wall: a) wall section with the marked slice location, b) deposits in the slice as seen in the segmented XRT scan, c) deposits and local gas velocity magnitude predicted by the simulation. Deposited particles = red, substrate = grey.

Figure 10: Comparison of the predicted and scanned particle deposits for time 50 s at $y = 143 \mu\text{m}$, which is ca. $93 \mu\text{m}$ deep inside the wall: a) wall section with the marked slice location, b) deposits in the slice as seen in the segmented XRT scan, c) deposits and local gas velocity magnitude predicted by the simulation. Deposited particles = red, substrate = grey.

Figure 11: Comparison of the predicted and scanned particle deposits for time 50 s at $y = 174 \mu\text{m}$, which is ca. $124 \mu\text{m}$ deep inside the wall: a) wall section with the marked slice location, b) deposits in the slice as seen in the segmented XRT scan, c) deposits and local gas velocity magnitude predicted by the simulation. Deposited particles = red, substrate = grey.

Figure 12: 3D reconstructed section of filter wall with gas streamlines for samples BF1, CF1, CF2, CF3 (a-d), and soot deposits with local volume fraction $\varphi_{s,P} > 0.1$ after reaching the filtration efficiency 99.9% (e-h). Substrate = grey, catalytic coating = yellow, particles = red, sample BF1 (bare) (a,e), CF1 (in-wall) (b,f), CF2 (combined) (c,g), and CF3 (on-wall) (d,h).

417 lower amount of soot deposits to reach the complete filtration efficiency, Fig-
 418 ure 12f. This is in line with the reduced volume of the wall pores that are
 419 partly occupied by the coated catalyst. Still, a relatively large part of soot
 420 penetrated inside the wall structure, particularly in the pathway of the largest
 421 permeating pore in the middle of the reconstructed section, as indicated by the
 422 gas streamlines.

423 The sample CF2 with part of the coating located on top of the wall shows
 424 a reduced soot penetration depth, Figure 12g. Though there are still few dom-
 425 inant permeation pathways, they lead mostly through the cracks and other
 426 imperfections in the coated layer on top of the wall. These narrower passages
 427 are soon closed by the soot deposits and the deep bed filtration is finished. The
 428 sample CF3 with a continuous layer of the catalyst on top of the wall shows

Figure 13: Predicted evolution of filtration efficiency depending on particle diameter with increasing soot deposit per volume of the whole filter: a) the sample BF1 (bare substrate), b) the sample CF1 (catalytic coating in the wall).

429 practically no penetration of soot and the deposits remain on the external sur-
 430 face, Figure 12h. In this case, just a little amount of soot is needed to reach the
 431 complete filtration efficiency.

432 The predicted evolution of filtration efficiency depending on the soot particle
 433 diameter and the accumulated soot mass is shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14.
 434 For the soot particles around 100–200 nm, direct interception is the dominant
 435 filtration regime and the efficiency does not depend much on the particle diam-
 436 eter. On the other hand, filtration efficiency of the smaller particles grows due
 437 to increasing impact of Brownian motion [28]. The accumulated soot mass is
 438 recalculated from the simulated microscopic section of the wall to the volume
 439 of the whole monolith, using the wall thickness and channel density values pro-
 440 vided in Section 2. Geometric surface area (GSA) density of inlet channels in

Figure 14: Predicted evolution of filtration efficiency depending on particle diameter with increasing soot deposit per volume of the whole filter: a) the sample CF2 (catalytic coating combination in & partly on the wall), b) the sample CF3 (catalytic coating mainly on the wall).

441 the studied samples is $1\,178\text{ m}^2\text{ m}^{-3}$; an interested reader can use this value to
442 convert the presented soot loading in mg/m^3 (soot mass per monolith volume)
443 to mg/m^2 (soot mass per filtration area).

444 Somewhat counter-intuitively, the clean filtration efficiency of the bare sam-
445 ple BF1 is slightly higher than that of CF1 with the in-wall catalyst coating,
446 Figure 13. This phenomenon was already reported before in experimental and
447 simulation studies [30, 32, 58] and is explained as follows. As a certain part of
448 the wall pores is blocked by the coating, the local gas flow rate in the remaining
449 free pores is higher, which may slightly decrease the filtration efficiency. How-
450 ever, during the filtration process, the sample CF1 shows much faster formation
451 of soot cake than BF1 and its filtration efficiency increases more quickly with
452 the deposited soot mass, Figure 13. The amount of deposited soot required to
453 reach the 99.9% filtration efficiency in the coated sample CF1 is more than ten
454 times lower than in the bare filter BF1.

455 Kong et al. [32] measured filtration efficiency evolution for bare and in-wall
456 coated GPF samples and reported soot loadings needed for reaching nearly com-
457 plete filtration efficiency. For the in-wall coated GPF, nearly complete filtration
458 efficiency was observed after soot loading of $99\text{ mg}/\text{dm}^3$ at the space velocity
459 of $32\,000\text{ h}^{-1}$, which gives superficial gas velocity through the filter wall similar
460 to the value used in our simulations. At the same soot loading, the measured
461 filtration efficiency of the bare GPF at the most penetrating particle size was
462 around 85%. Though the bare and in-wall coated filter structures investigated
463 experimentally by Kong et al. [32] were not identical to our samples BF1 and
464 CF1, their measured evolution of filtration efficiency curve with soot loading
465 revealed similar trends to those predicted by our model, Figure 13.

466 The initial clean filtration efficiency increases with the catalytic coating lo-
467 cated in the on-wall layer, see the results for the samples CF2 and CF3 in
468 Figure 14. Co-currently, the deposited soot mass required to reach the com-
469 plete filtration efficiency decreases, which means that the whole process becomes
470 much faster.

471 Figure 15 compares the transient evolution of average filtration efficiency

472 for all the studied samples. The sample CF3 with a continuous catalyst layer
 473 on top of the wall reaches the complete filtration efficiency within 15 minutes
 474 of its operation. The sample CF2 with non-compact catalytic layer on the
 475 wall requires 85 minutes of soot accumulation, and the sample CF1 with just
 476 the in-wall catalyst coating reaches the full filtration efficiency after 4 hours.
 477 The bare sample BF1 needs much more time on stream and, though its initial
 478 filtration efficiency is higher than that of CF1, reaches the efficiency of 99.9%
 479 only after more than 60 hours of operation. It must be considered that the
 480 studied substrate BF1 was designed specifically for the application with catalytic
 481 coating – it is highly porous and contains larger pores than bare filters intended

Figure 15: Predicted average filtration efficiency evolution for the samples with different distribution of catalytic coating. (a) time scale relevant to the coated samples CF1–CF3, (b) time scale showing complete curve for the bare sample BF1.

Figure 16: Predicted wall pressure drop evolution for the samples with different distribution of catalytic coating. (a) time scale relevant to the coated samples CF1–CF3, (b) time scale showing complete curve for the bare sample BF1.

482 for direct use [59]. This makes BF1 rather inefficient when the coating is not
 483 applied.

484 The corresponding evolution of pressure drop over the wall of the individual
 485 samples is shown in Figure 16. Note that the pressure drop of the whole fil-
 486 ter consists of contraction/expansion effects at the channel inlet/outlet, friction
 487 along the channel, and pressure drop over the wall [29]. The micro-scale model
 488 used in this simulation study accounts just for the evolution of the latter contri-
 489 bution. With a relatively thin cake, the other two contributions remain similar
 490 to the clean filter and the computed evolution of wall pressure drop represents
 491 well the overall change. However, when the on-wall cake gets thick and occupies
 492 a significant part of the channel cross-section, the pressure drop at the channel

493 inlet as well as the friction along the channel start to contribute to the increase
494 of pressure drop. Modelling of this impact is out of the scope of this paper and
495 we focus solely on the pressure drop over the wall.

496 Figure 16 reveals that the superior clean filtration efficiency of the sample
497 CF3 with a continuous catalytic layer on top of the wall is accompanied by a
498 high initial pressure drop, which further increases during soot accumulation.
499 The slope of pressure drop curve is quite steep from the beginning but grad-
500 ually decreases and becomes significantly milder after 15 minutes, indicating
501 transition from deep bed to cake filtration regime. After ca. 1 hour, the slope
502 stabilizes and pressure drop increase of CF3 becomes linear as expected in cake
503 filtration.

504 The combined sample CF2 possesses cracks and local openings in its thinner
505 on-wall layer, which significantly decreases the initial pressure drop in compar-
506 ison to the uniform layer of coating present in the sample CF3, Figure 16. The
507 soot accumulation period needed to close the open pathways in the CF2 wall
508 and reach the complete filtration efficiency is longer, but the final pressure drop
509 after transition to the cake filtration regime is approximately 65% lower than in
510 CF3. The final slopes of the pressure drop curve in CF2 and CF3 are similar,
511 confirming the transition to cake filtration regime.

512 The sample CF1 with the catalyst deposited only inside the wall exhibits
513 the lowest initial pressure drop from the three coated samples. There is also
514 a significant lag in the CF1 pressure drop increase after the start of the filtra-
515 tion process – almost no change in pressure can be seen within the first hour
516 of operation, Figure 16. This is caused by the relatively low clean filtration
517 efficiency and large open pores present in the CF1 structure. It takes a consid-
518 erable amount of time to build a significant deposits in the CF1 wall pores before
519 they start to affect the pressure drop. When the CF1 pressure drop evolution
520 is compared to the corresponding filtration efficiency curve in Figure 15, it can
521 be concluded that the effect of the deposited soot on the filtration efficiency is
522 immediate, while the impact on pressure drop develops with a certain delay.
523 On the other hand, when the pressure drop starts to grow, its slope is quite

524 high and continues even after 4 hours of operation, when the complete filtration
525 efficiency has been reached. This indicates ongoing deep bed filtration regime
526 with filling the wall pores by the deposited soot. The cake filtration regime,
527 with a milder slope and linear pressure drop curve is not reached even after
528 more than 8 hours of operation.

529 The extensive deep filtration period of the sample CF1 leads to a noticeably
530 higher final pressure drop compared to the sample CF2 with its partial on-wall
531 coating that speeds up the transition to cake filtration regime. The sample CF2
532 thus outperforms CF1 not only in terms of filtration efficiency but also when
533 comparing the pressure drop after soot loading; the benefit of the low initial
534 pressure drop of CF1 is lost during the filtration process, Figure 15. The on-
535 wall catalytic layer of CF2 with a lower pore-size acts as an efficient filtration
536 membrane, the beneficial effect of which was observed also in other studies of
537 wall structures with non-uniform distribution of porosity [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19].
538 However, such a membrane must be very thin to keep acceptably low pressure
539 drop, which disqualifies the sample CF3.

540 **5. Conclusions**

541 The developed pore-scale model of particle deposition in the filter wall struc-
542 ture was first validated against time-resolved X-Ray tomography data acquired
543 during the filtration experiment. The validated model was then used for simula-
544 tions of soot deposition in different filter structures utilizing the same cordierite
545 substrate with different distribution of catalytic coating.

546 The results revealed that the best trade-off between high filtration efficiency
547 and low pressure drop can be obtained with a combined catalytic coating lo-
548 cated both inside and on top of the filter wall. The sample CF3 with practically
549 all catalyst on top of the wall provided an excellent clean filtration efficiency but
550 unacceptably high pressure drop. The sample CF1 coated only inside the wall
551 provided the lowest initial pressure drop that, however, increased significantly
552 with time on stream as a result of deep filtration. The sample CF2, possessing

553 part of the catalytic material in a thin catalytic layer on top of the wall, showed
554 faster transition to the cake filtration regime, leaving the wall pores free and
555 achieving lower pressure drop after soot loading. The predicted evolution of
556 particle deposits and their impact on the filter function is relevant also to accu-
557 mulation of incombustible ash, which becomes dominant component deposited
558 in a filter after long-term use.

559 The particle accumulation model presented in this paper together with the
560 convection-reaction-diffusion model for catalyzed reactions of gaseous pollutants
561 [25] represent a powerful toolbox for further tuning of catalyst distribution on/in
562 the filter wall. These simulation tools help to reach the ultimate goal for the
563 practical application – the development of microstructures with optimum per-
564 formance over the whole operating cycle of a catalytic filter.

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569 **Appendix A. Flow profiles along the channel**

570 The uniformity of flow through the filter wall along the channel during the
 571 XRT experiment was studied by a 3D channel-scale model. The model uses
 572 the same governing equations for gas flow as presented in Section 3.1. The
 573 computational domain was a replica of the 3x3 channels sample with single
 574 central inlet channel. The filter wall in this simulation was approximated by a
 575 porous layer with effective permeability $2.87 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$, the value of which was
 576 obtained from 3D pore-scale simulations of flow through the wall section BF0.

577 Figure A.1a shows 2D cross-section slice in the middle of the domain colored
 578 by the magnitude of gas velocity along the channel (u_z). The corresponding
 579 profile of gas velocity through the filter wall (u_y) is depicted in Figure A.1b.
 580 The simulation confirms relatively uniform flow profile through the wall with
 581 mean superficial velocity 0.0026 m s^{-1} . Note that the profile in Figure A.1b
 582 would become less uniform at higher flow rates [29].

Figure A.1: 3D channel simulation of BF0 sample experimental set-up: a) 2D cross-section slice displaying gas velocity along the channel u_z , b) profile of gas velocity through the filter wall u_y along the channel.

583 **Nomenclature**

b	Sutherland equation parameter, $\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1/2}$
d	diameter, m
F	force, N
m	mass, kg
N	number concentration, $\# \text{m}^{-3}$
\mathcal{P}	probability of particle trapping, 1
p	pressure, Pa
S	Sutherland equation parameter, K
T	temperature, K
t	time, s
u	linear velocity, m s^{-1}
x	spatial coordinate perpendicular to the flow direction, m
y	spatial coordinate in the flow direction, m

Greek letters

ε	porosity, 1
φ	volume fraction, 1
κ	Darcy's permeability, m^2
μ	dynamic viscosity, Pa s
ν	kinematic viscosity, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
Ω	computational domain
Ω_P	cell in computational domain
Ω_N	face-neighbour of Ω_P
ρ	density, kg m^{-3}

Subscripts and superscripts

B	Brownian
c	coated catalyst (porous)
D	drag

in	inlet
p	particle
s	soot deposit (porous)

Abbreviations

CFD	computational fluid dynamics
DPF	diesel particulate filter
GPF	gasoline particulate filter
GSA	geometric surface area
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann method
MIP	mercury intrusion porosimetry
PF	particulate filter
PM	particulate matter
XRT	X-ray (micro)tomography

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